

covered with 11- × 55-cm nylon mesh cages. Twenty female black bugs/cage were allowed to oviposit for 24 h. Ten pots were flooded 10.5 cm deep for 24 h. Ten pots were watered to 4.0 cm. After the water level was reduced to expose the egg masses, 5 female egg parasites *T. triptus* were introduced into each cage and allowed to search and oviposit for 3 d.

Black bug egg masses deposited on plants totaled 147 in flooded pots and 110 in unflooded pots. The egg masses were held in individual tubes until nymphs hatched or parasites emerged.

As a whole, flooding increased egg parasitization: 17% in unflooded pots and 54% in flooded pots (see figure). The difference was attributed to disturbance of the female during flooding, exposing the egg masses to *T. triptus*. However, parasite emergence was significantly lower from egg masses on flooded plants (18%) than from egg masses on unflooded plants (42%). □

Effect of flooding on parasitization of black bug eggs by *Telenomus triptus*. Values are significantly different at the 5% level according to student *t*-test.

Host range and overwintering of rice pink stem borer (PSB) in a hilly region of India

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PSB *Sesamia inferens* Walk. occurs regularly in the hilly region of Uttar Pradesh. The pest is active May-Oct. The polyphagous species may attack a number of other graminaceous plants. To identify its host range, we studied infestations at experimental farms, Hawalbagh (1,250 m above sea level), and adjacent areas.

This region has two distinct crop seasons. In the winter (Nov-May), wheat and barley and some pulses are grown. In the summer (Jun-Oct), crops are primarily rice, maize, and some pulses and millet. Rice is also planted in winter fallow fields in the spring (Mar-Apr).

A number of crops were found to be infested by PSB. The maximum susceptibility was exhibited by

Crops infested by PSB in U.P. hills, India.

Common name	Botanical name	Severity of infestation
Sorghum	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	Moderate
Maize	<i>Zea mays</i>	Low-moderate
Ragi (finger millet)	<i>Eleusine coracana</i>	Low-moderate
Barnyard millet	<i>Echinochloa frumentacea</i>	Moderate-high
Foxtail millet	<i>Setaria italica</i>	Low
Proso millet	<i>Panicum miliaceum</i>	Low
Kodo millet	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i>	Low
Rice	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	
Spring, rainfed direct seeded		Moderate
June planted, rainfed upland		Moderate
Irrigated transplanted		High
Wheat	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	Low
Barley	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Low
Oat	<i>Avena sativa</i>	Low

transplanted irrigated rice (see table). Barnyard millet was another preferred host. Infestation also was found in winter crops such as wheat and barley at later growth stages, primarily from the end of Apr to May.

Studies on overwintering showed that larvae remained dormant in winter, hibernating in rice stubbles from the end of Oct to Mar. Hibernating larvae were slightly larger than their normal mature

size. Only older larvae overwintered; the younger larvae died.

Overwintering larvae changed into the pupal stage between the end of Mar and the beginning of Apr, with the onset of warmer weather. Moths usually emerged from mid-Apr on.

It seems that the moths of this generation lay eggs on spring rice, wheat, or barley; thus, the larvae of this generation damage these crops. As the

winters are extremely cold in the hills (temperature often below 0 °C), only a few of the overwintering larvae survive. High infestations are caused mainly by the second generation larvae resulting from the mass egg laying during Jul-Aug. □

Chemical control of rice stem borers (SB) in the Punjab

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Three SB species—*Scirpophaga incertulas*, *S. innotata*, and *Sesamia inferens*—damage rice in the Punjab. *S. incertulas* is predominant. Damage has been recorded in rice nurseries in certain pockets of Amritsar, Ferozpur, and Faridkot districts.

SB incidence has increased during the last 2 yr. Staggered sowing over a longer period, an increase in the area under irrigation, growing unapproved susceptible varieties, and other agronomic manipulations appear to be

Effect of different insecticides on incidence of rice SB.^a Punjab, India.

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Incidence (% whiteheads)	Yield (t/ha)
Cartap hydrochloride 4 G	1.5	3.8 a	5.3 a
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.0	26.4 bed	3.2 d
Carbofuran 3 G	1.0	25.4 bc	4.2 b
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	0.5	20.2 b	4.2 b
Deltamethrin + buprofezin 5.9 EC	0.09	33.3 d	3.1 d
Phosalone 35 EC	0.5	26.1 bed	3.8 c
Control	—	32.3 cd	2.4 e

^aIn a column, values designated by different letters are statistically different (Duncan's multiple range test).

factors in the increase.

Control of SB is with insecticides. We evaluated two new granular compounds, chlorpyrifos 10 G and cartap hydrochloride 4 G, with carbofuran 3 G as the standard. Chlorpyrifos 40 EC, deltamethrin + buprofezin 5.9 EC, and phosalone 35 EC as foliar spray also were evaluated.

Recommended variety PR103 was grown in 17-m² plots in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Single applications of chemicals were given the first week of Sep 1986, when the crop was nearly 40 d old and when deadhearts reached 5%.

Among the granular insecticides, cartap hydrochloride was most effective (see table). Average whitehead incidence was only 3.8%, compared to 25.4% with carbofuran and 26.4% with chlorpyrifos 10 G. Foliar application of chlorpyrifos 40 EC showed 20.2% incidence, significantly lower than deltamethrin + buprofezin but statistically equal to phosalone.

The significantly highest yield was with cartap hydrochloride. Cartap hydrochloride 4 G granular insecticide at 1.5 kg ai/ha controlled rice SB and promoted yield. □

Monitoring susceptibility of rice pests to insecticides

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Following FAO/IRRI workshops—“Judicious and Efficient Use of Insecticides on Rice” (1983) and “Monitoring Susceptibility Levels of Rice Pests to Insecticides” (1984)—12

Asian rice-growing countries formed a network to establish baseline insecticide susceptibility of major rice pests.

Susceptibility to insecticides was determined by topical application with the Kiya hand-operated microapplicator and a calibrated microsyringe. A specified volume of insecticides for each test insect was applied on the thoracic tergites (Table 1). Treated insects were transferred through a funnel to minimize mechanical damage to plastic tumbler cages containing 8-10 2-wk-old TN1 seedlings.

Larvae were transferred to petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and provided with cut leaves or diet for stem borer. The tests usually had 3 replications, with at least 15 insects/replication. Cages and petri dishes were kept in an incubator or controlled room at 25-30 °C, 60-80% relative humidity, and 12-h light. Larval

mortality was recorded 24, 48, and 72 h after treatment. LD₅₀/LD₉₅ values of the insecticides were computed using probit analysis.

Five countries have established susceptibility baseline data for *N. lugens* (Table 2). Indonesia had relatively higher LD₅₀ values with three insecticides, indicating that *N. lugens* in Indonesia may be less susceptible to insecticides. However, *N. lugens* from two collection sites did not show much

Table 1. Rice insect pests and volume of insecticides applied.

Insect pest	Volume applied (μl)
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>	1.0
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	0.5
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	0.2
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	0.1
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	0.1